

**Critical evaluation of key parameters in single particle ICP-MS data processing
for the correct determination of platinum nanoparticles in complex environmental
and biological matrices**

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Abstract

There is an urgent need for the harmonization of critical parameters in single particle inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (SP-ICP-MS) and they have been deeply studied and optimized in the present work using platinum nanoparticles (PtNPs) as a representative case of study. Special attention has been paid for data processing in order to achieve an adequate discrimination between signals. Thus, a comparison between four different algorithms has been performed and the method for transport efficiency calculation **has** also been severely evaluated (finding the use of a well characterized solution of the same targeted analyte (30 nm PtNPs) as adequate). The best results **have been** obtained after the application of a deconvolution approach for the data processing, and using 5 ms as dwell time and 40,000 data points for **data** acquisition. Under the optimized conditions, a correct discrimination between NP events and background signal up to 100 or 750 ng L⁻¹ of added ionic Pt was reached for 30 and 50 nm PtNPs, respectively. The suitability of the developed **method** for the characterization of PtNPs in relevant environmental (water samples) and biological (cell culture media) matrices has also been demonstrated.

Keywords

Platinum nanoparticles, ionic platinum, single particle inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry, data processing, signal discrimination, complex matrices.

1. Introduction

During the last decade, single particle inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (SP-ICP-MS) has emerged as one of the most powerful and versatile techniques to study metallic nanoparticles (NPs) [1]. It can provide relevant analytical information both in terms of size and concentration in a particle-by-particle basis [2]. However, this technique is conditioned by several assumptions regarding data acquisition and processing **that are hindering its application in routine and** must be carefully considered to obtain reliable results.

Critical parameters influencing SP-ICP-MS data acquisition should be thoroughly addressed to improve signal discrimination (**between NP events and background**), being the most remarkable those such as dwell time, the measured data points, transport efficiency calculation, or sample dilution [3]. **Working with the adequate dwell time and data points will be crucial for a correct determination of the particle number concentration (PNC) and size distribution [4, 5]. Dilution can help to minimize the risk of measure two NPs at the same time (multiple events), but if the sample is too diluted the frequency of events would be too low and subsequently lead to long times to measure representative data sets [2, 6].** Other key parameter is the transport efficiency and the method for its calculation. Usually, it is considered to be the “Achilles heel” of this technique if traditional pneumatic aspiration is employed. By improving the transport efficiency, more reliable results will be obtained. Higher transport efficiencies also mean less time to measure representative data sets, which would be beneficial from a metrological point of view [3, 6]. **Regarding this,** there are several methods to calculate the transport efficiency that can be categorized in two major types, direct or indirect. The first ones are based on the use of a certified reference NP with a known PNC or size [7]. But the shortage of suitable certified reference NPs (stock or specific of each NP) is a major issue for these

estimations, and other novel alternatives have arisen. One of these new indirect approaches is the dynamic mass flow method proposed by the group of Goenaga-Infante [8]. It is a gravimetric approach that does not require the use of any certified NP, but is complex and time-consuming. Nevertheless, there is still a lack of consensus about how the transport efficiency can be more effectively calculated.

Another challenge that SP-ICP-MS faces is the data processing step to accurately discriminate NP signals, especially those of the smallest sizes, from the continuous background signal. Nowadays, there is no standardized method to distinguish those signals [9]. As an attempt to fill this gap, some authors have developed home-built software [10, 11] to integrate the different data processing algorithms and advance towards a harmonization of this step. Usually, threshold limits of a number of times of the standard deviation (denoted by σ) from the continuous signal have been used [12]. During the last years, σ values from 3 to 8 have been applied, but recently, 5 has been described as the best option to reduce the occurrence of false positives to virtually 0 for Poisson baseline distributions [12]. In some cases, this approach treats incorrectly background signals as NP, overestimating the number of small NPs [5]. Also, it can arbitrarily classify NP signals as background, especially in cases where more than 5σ would work better as threshold [12, 13]. The setting of threshold limits based on outlier analysis seem to introduce a bias, specially, for challenging situations, when overlap between signals may occur, such as the analysis of complex samples. In these cases, the use of a deconvolution approach [14] appears to be more suitable. This method is based on the fitting of polygaussian probability mass functions to frequencies of the lowest signal intensities such as those of blanks or dissolved ions and the subsequent subtraction of the dissolved signal component. Other alternative is to apply a K-clustering algorithm, proposed by Bi *et al.* (2014), which defines groups in the data set based on

their similarity [15]. This approach needs the optimization of the K value for each situation, that is crucial for an optimum discrimination, making this option arduous to perform [15]. Therefore, the performance of reliable studies of NPs in complex matrices using SP-ICP-MS is still an arduous task due to the lack of harmonization for the data acquisition and processing conditions and a thorough optimization would be needed.

Thus, this work is devoted to the development and critical evaluation of an analytical **method** based on SP-ICP-MS for the correct characterization and quantification of NPs in terms of size distribution, and PNC. As a case of study, platinum nanoparticles (PtNPs) have been investigated due to their interesting properties for many biomedical [16], technological and daily products **applications**, which comes with an increase of their release into the environment, and the subsequential human exposure [17]. Different methods for data processing based on distinct algorithms have been rigorously evaluated and compared. Also, key acquisition parameters, such as dwell time, data points, dilution effect, and the method for the calculation of the transport efficiency have been thoroughly optimized. Additionally, the applicability of the optimized **method** for the discrimination between ionic and NP forms of Pt under co-existence conditions, and the characterization of PtNPs in relevant environmental and biological matrices has been **addressed**.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Chemical and reagents

All chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade. Solutions were prepared in ultrapure water (18.2 **MΩ-cm**), obtained from a Milli-Q[®] A10[™] water purification system (Millipore Corporation, USA). **Details of all reagents are given in the Electronic Supporting Material (ESM, Supplementary text, Section 1).**

Commercial solutions of 30 and 50 nm PtNPs, and 30 nm AuNPs stabilized in 2 mM citrate were purchased from NanoComposix (USA). **Characterization of those solutions is provided in the ESM (Supplementary text, Section 2).** Before their use, all NP solutions were homogenized 1 min with vortex agitation (using an advanced ZX3 Vortex from Velp Scientifica, Italy) at 1,200 rpm to prevent NP aggregation. Then, they were diluted to accomplish the SP-ICP-MS requirements stated in previous works [4, 13, 18]. Also, more challenging situations which exceeds these typical working conditions were considered.

2.2 SP-ICP-MS analysis: instrumental conditions and data processing

A triple quadrupole ICP-MS iCap-TQ (Thermo Electron Corporation, Germany), equipped with a Micromist nebulizer and a cyclonic spray chamber, was employed for SP-ICP-MS analysis. Operational conditions are summarized in Table 1. The equipment was tuned daily for the highest sensitivity in the Single Quadrupole Kinetic Energy Discrimination mode (SQ-KED) with He as collision gas. Raw signal data were processed using different methods and algorithms by means of the npQuant plug-in of Qtegra™ Intelligent Scientific Data Solution™ (ISDS) and Nanocount version 3.2 software [11] to obtain the size distribution and PNC. These calculations were performed using the density of Pt and mass fraction of PtNPs, and assuming that NPs are spherical and solid. The data of a particle solution (30 nm PtNPs with a nominal size of 32 ± 3 nm at $5.28 \cdot 10^4$ p mL⁻¹) was used in each series of measurements as reference to determine the transport efficiency, and for the calculations of particle size and concentrations. The response factor of the ionic analyte standard must also be known and was calculated using different standards (100 to 2,000 ng L⁻¹) of ionic Pt. The sample flow rate was estimated daily by measuring the mass of water taken up by the instrument for 5 min. This measurement was performed by duplicate. Concentration and size limit of detection (LOD_c and LOD_{size}, respectively) were calculated using the spreadsheet proposed by Laborda *et al.* (2020)

[12]. Particle events in corresponding blanks were measured and subtracted through all the experiments.

Table 1. SP-ICP-MS operating conditions

RF-Power (KW)	1.5
Plasma gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	14
Carrier gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	1
Nebulizer flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	1.0
Auxiliary gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	0.8
Nebulizer	Meinhard type
Spray chamber	Cyclonic type
Isotope monitored	¹⁹⁵ Pt
Analyte mass (u.m.a)	194.96
Density (g cm ⁻³)	21.45
Mode	SQ-KED
He flow rate (mL min ⁻¹)	4.9
Q1 Bias (V)	-2.5
QCell Bias (V)	-2.0
Q3 Bias (V)	-1.0
Transport efficiency (%)	9 – 12
Sample flow rate (mL min ⁻¹)	0.32 – 0.40
Dwell time (ms)	5
Acquisition time (s)	200
Data points	40,000

2.3 Sample preparation

Synthetic water referred as moderately hard water was prepared following a U.S. Environmental Protection Agency protocol (EPA-821-R-02-12) [19], in presence (2 mg

L⁻¹) or absence of humic acid (HA). Chemical composition and characterization are provided in Table S1. Tap water sample was taken from our laboratory after letting flow for 5 min. Two different water samples (W#1 and W#2) were collected in locations along the Tagus River in Castilla – La Mancha region, Spain. Global positioning system (GPS) coordinates and water characteristics are presented in Table S2.

For the experiments with cell culture media, Dulbecco's modified eagle medium (DMEM)-High glucose was used either directly or supplemented with a mixture of antibiotics (100 U mL⁻¹ of penicillin and 100 µg mL⁻¹ streptomycin) or a combination of these antibiotics with 10 % of fetal bovine serum (FBS).

A series of dilutions ($3.02 \cdot 10^4 - 1.06 \cdot 10^5$ p mL⁻¹) of 30 nm PtNPs were mixed in each of the studied matrices (water samples and cell culture media) in absence or presence of different reagents (2 % HCl, 0.1 % Cysteine (Cys), or a mixture of them). In all cases, samples were homogenized by vortex agitation for 10 s.

3. Results and discussion

During the optimization process of this SP-ICP-MS based method, critical parameters have been meticulously addressed for an accurate determination of PtNP size distribution (nm), and PNC (p mL⁻¹) with special focus on data processing. Recoveries (%) were calculated as the found PNC relative to the spiked PNC.

3.1 Comparison of data processing algorithms

Dilution is an important factor when working with this technique because if samples are not sufficiently or too diluted, size and concentrations would be determined in a wrong way. There are two potential scenarios that would respond to different statistical distributions. On one hand, the frequency distribution of samples with low intensity

signals will follow a Poisson distribution [2, 4]. Some authors recommend selecting the dilution based on a ratio between the desired NP events in the plasma and the number of total data points [4, 13, 18]. Commonly, under well-established data processing conditions (such as 5- σ criterion) it is accepted that a ratio of 0.1 is enough for an adequate size determination, but to obtain reliable PNC results, this ratio has to be 0.05 [13, 18]. On the other hand, if samples have a high dissolved or particle concentration (or both combined) their frequency distribution will follow a Polygaussian distribution, other data processing conditions that attend to this particular issue should be applied, such as the deconvolution approach [14]. Thus, in order to cover both scenarios, samples containing 30 or 50 nm PtNPs individually were diluted in ultrapure water covering a range from $1.06 \cdot 10^4$ to $3.02 \cdot 10^5$ p mL⁻¹ through all the experiments (which corresponds to ratios from ≈ 0.03 to 0.75), calculated taking an average value of transport efficiency of 10 ± 0.4 %, ($n = 6$). Regarding the data acquisition, 5 ms was initially established as dwell time (based on previous studies with PtNPs [20]), and the number of data points used were 30,000, until their optimization in **ESM (Supplementary text, Section 3)**. Under these conditions, samples **can** be divided into two main groups, the ones that will match Poisson statistics ($1.06 \cdot 10^4$ to $5.28 \cdot 10^4$ p mL⁻¹), and those with higher intensities that will follow a Polygaussian distribution ($1.06 \cdot 10^5$ to $3.02 \cdot 10^5$ p mL⁻¹).

Four different algorithms to discriminate between PtNPs and the background signal to obtain information of size and concentration have been tested. Thus, the proprietary software of the ICP-MS instrument (npQuant plug-in from Thermo Electron Corporation), a well established approach (5- σ criterion) [12], an option based on K-clustering algorithm [15], and a deconvolution method stated by Cornelis *et al.* (2014) [11, 14] **have been** compared. Their performance to determine recovery (%) using the initial acquisition conditions mentioned above has been tested. The mean registered

particle events in three consecutive blanks ($n = 3$) were measured and calculated for each case. Thus, the false positives arising from the background signal were subtracted. Obtained recoveries using the software npQuant for 30 nm PtNPs (Figure 1A) were lower as long as the PtNP concentration raises. But, for 50 nm PtNPs (Figure 1B), this decrease is not noticeable up to samples above the Poisson requirements ($5.28 \cdot 10^4 \text{ p mL}^{-1}$). This software works with pre-fixed upper and lower thresholds, which are selected based on the frequency distribution of a reference NP. This fact can explain the low recoveries for most dilutions, since is not able to resolve changes in the frequency distribution.

Figure 1. Recoveries (%) for PtNP PNC (p mL^{-1}) of A) 30 nm and B) 50 nm PtNPs using 5- σ criterion (blue), K-means (red), np-Quant (yellow), and deconvolution (black)

as data processing method, (5 ms as dwell time, and 30.000 data points for data acquisition).

When the 5- σ criterion and high PtNP concentrations were used, the signal discrimination was very poor, obtaining a high percentage of false negatives. In this case, a correct signal discrimination was only achieved in a short range of concentrations ($1.06 \cdot 10^4 - 3.02 \cdot 10^4$ p mL⁻¹) for both PtNP sizes, since those samples will follow Poisson statistics correctly. Applying K-means (K = 2) results in a constant decreasing trend of the recoveries when the concentration raises consistent with that observed for np-Quant. Close to 100 % recoveries were obtained for 30 nm (Figure 1A) mainly at higher dilutions, but for 50 nm (Figure 1B), they were close to 80 % until the concentration raises above $1.06 \cdot 10^5$ p mL⁻¹. In the present work, K = 2 has been selected taking into account the literature [15]. This algorithm classifies signals based on their similarity, specifically into K groups with K centers (each center corresponding to a single group). Therefore, in an ideal situation, where only 2 groups are present in the sample (NP signals and background), 2 is selected as K value. However, this assumes a monodisperse NP solution, which is rarely the case. Thus, in a real situation like the one studied, part of the particle distribution is going to be addressed as background signals, causing an inaccurate signal discrimination. Lastly, when the deconvolution algorithm was applied, recoveries close to 100 % were reported in a wider range of PtNP concentrations (Figures 1A and B). Even though values achieved for PtNP sizes applying this algorithm were adequate, the ones obtained for 50 nm PtNPs were higher. This can be explained by its frequency distribution, which would be easily deconvolved from the dissolved one as its located further from the background signal distribution being less overlapped.

For SP-ICP-MS analysis, not only a correct concentration determination should be achieved, but also size distribution must be accurately determined. Regarding particle size

determination (Figure S1), when the software from the instrument **is used**, the calculated size remained almost constant for the two studied PtNP sizes (Figures S1A and B). Therefore, if changes in the frequency distribution are not resolved, the size seems to be not greatly disturbed. If $5\text{-}\sigma$ is applied as data processing method more biased results were obtained. In this case, size was correctly determined for both sizes in the same short range of concentrations, ($1.06\cdot 10^3 - 3.02\cdot 10^4 \text{ p mL}^{-1}$). Size determination under K-means algorithm was adequate for 30 nm PtNPs (Figure S1A) in all cases, but for 50 nm PtNPs (Figure S1B) it was overestimated. As explained early, the subjectiveness introduced by selecting this K value can produce the observed effects, as it can change completely particle size distribution. For deconvolution, following the same tendency observed for concentrations, size was accurately determined through all the concentrations studied.

In order to compare the performance of the different employed algorithms, the **linearity** was calculated, along with the LOD_{size} and LOD_c (Table 2). Deconvolution offers a wider linearity range since it can work with samples above the Poisson requirements [14]. Regarding LOD_{size} and LOD_c , there is no method to accurately calculate them using deconvolution or K-means, so, they were calculated following the definitions proposed by Laborda *et al.* (2020) for other data processing algorithms [12]. Even though lower values were achieved using deconvolution, significant differences were not found between them. As mentioned above, other data processing methods, like $5\text{-}\sigma$ criterion or K-means, can perform an accurate size and PNC but in a narrower range than deconvolution, probably because those works were conducted under samples following Poisson statistics and also because of the subjective bias than an outlier analysis introduces in the data processing, making the dilution range a restrictive condition for an SP-ICP-MS analysis. Thus, by using deconvolution, the dynamic concentration range

where those parameters are correctly studied can be expanded, since offers a better discrimination when overlapping of signals occurs [14].

Table 2. *PNC linear range* ($p \text{ mL}^{-1}$), concentration and size limits of detection (LOD) for the studied data processing algorithms.

Algorithm	PNC linear range	LOD _{size} (nm)	LOD _c ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)
NP-Quant ¹	$1.06 \cdot 10^4$ to $2.11 \cdot 10^5$	17.16	0.063
5- σ criterion ²	$1.06 \cdot 10^4$ to $3.02 \cdot 10^4$	16.95	0.077
K-means ³	$1.06 \cdot 10^4$ to $1.06 \cdot 10^5$	17.01	0.066
Deconvolution ⁴	$1.06 \cdot 10^4$ to $3.02 \cdot 10^5$	16.70	0.059

¹Software from Thermo Electron Corp.

²Refs. 7, and 12

³Ref. 15

⁴Ref. 14

3.2. Transport efficiency calculation method

The feasibility of the SP-ICP-MS analysis relies on the transport efficiency calculation. Therefore, the correct estimation of this parameter becomes crucial. As a rule of thumb, a direct method based on the size of AuNP reference standards [7], such as NIST RM 8011, 8012, and 8013 or LGC QC5050, has been used for transport efficiencies calculations for a variety of metallic NPs including PtNPs [6, 9, 21–24]. But the limited availability of an adequate reference NP made this direct approach challenging. Moreover, this method based on a standard NP relies on the element sensitivity as one of the parameters to do the calculations, so it would be of paramount interest to use NP reference materials of the same element, since differences between element's sensitivities are usually reported [4, 9]. Therefore, a well-characterized NP with the same core that the target NP appears to be the most convenient direct approach for that task.

After a study of other acquisition parameters, such as dwell time and data points (ESM, Supplementary text, Section 3), where 5 ms and 40,000 data points were found as optimum, different methods for the estimation of transport efficiency have been compared. This parameter was calculated using either a solution of 30 nm PtNPs purchased at NanoComposix (32 ± 3 nm) or the LGC QC5050 AuNPs standard (33 ± 2 nm). A novel gravimetric method, which is based on indirect assumptions and does not need the use of any reference NP, has also been tested (Table S3) [8]. No remarkable differences were observed between the transport efficiencies (Table S3) obtained using the distinct approaches. It involves that no statistically significant differences were found ($p < 0.05$) in the determination of PtNP size and concentration when applying the different values (Table S3).

As previously stated, transport efficiency calculations are based on many assumptions (e.g., element density and sensitivity, or the certified size) [7]. Accordingly, to reduce the uncertainty (or assumed error) on those calculations, improve the transport efficiency values and the simplicity of the analysis routine, the use of a NP made from the same element that the targeted analyte (Pt in this case) as reference appears to be beneficial. Therefore, we suggest this option while appropriate certified materials with known particle size are available. Regarding the application of the indirect approach, its use can be suitable to calculate the transport efficiency in situations where certified reference materials are lacking [8]. However, this method is time consuming and arduous to perform, so it can be mainly considered as a control tool to check the accuracy of the determined size of a NP solution before being used as reference for the other methods.

Even so, all transport efficiencies obtained were below 15 %. This is a typical drawback for SP-ICP-MS methodologies if traditional aspiration based on regular-flow nebulizers and cyclonic spray chambers are employed [6]. Due to technological limitations, the

improvement of this value **can** just be achieved if other aspiration devices are used. In this sense, there are several alternatives based on pneumatic nebulization such as microdroplet generator or total consumption chambers, where values close to 100 % **can** even be reached **that can be explored** [25].

3.3 Study of discrimination capabilities

Final optimized SP-ICP-MS operating conditions are summarized in Table 1. As a proof of applicability for the discrimination of different NP sizes, mixtures of 30 and 50 nm PtNPs at different concentrations ($1.06 \cdot 10^4 - 1.06 \cdot 10^5 \text{ p mL}^{-1}$ for each NP) were analysed **using deconvolution as data processing algorithm**, providing an accurate size and concentration determination of both PtNPs. As an example, the frequency histogram after the deconvolution treatment as well as the final particle size distribution of a mixture of 30 and 50 nm PtNPs at intermediate concentrations ($5.28 \cdot 10^4 \text{ p mL}^{-1}$ for each NP) **are** shown in **Figure S6**.

One of the main goals of a SP-ICP-MS **method** is to achieve a correct discrimination of ionic (or dissolved) and NP signals, since both forms can co-exist, and the performance of the analysis should not be affected by this fact. In this regard, the developed **method** was tested under situations where this discrimination between signals **can** be difficult, leading to errors in the determination of the concentration and size. For that aim, two sizes of PtNPs (30 and 50 nm) were mixed individually ($\approx 5 \cdot 10^4 \text{ p mL}^{-1}$) or jointly with increasing concentrations of ionic Pt (0 – 4,000 ng L⁻¹). Regarding concentration (**Figure 2**), quantitative recoveries were obtained up to 100 ng L⁻¹ of ionic Pt for 30 nm, and 750 ng L⁻¹ for 50 nm and the mixture of both PtNP sizes. Larger dissolved concentrations in each situation lead to underestimation in the concentration, being most of the PtNPs regarded as ionic signals.

Figure 2. Recoveries (%) of PtNPs at increasing ionic platinum concentrations for 30 (blue), 50 nm (red) PtNPs, or a mixture of both PtNPs (black) at a concentration of $\approx 5 \cdot 10^4 \text{ p mL}^{-1}$ each.

The higher value for 50 nm and the mixture can be attributed to the higher intensity frequencies that are needed to produce signal overlapping. Size was accurately determined (Figure S7) for a larger range of added ionic Pt concentrations even though concentration was not correctly determined in some of these cases. For 30 nm, size was overestimated when more than 500 ng L⁻¹ of ionic Pt is added, alone (Figure S7A) or mixed with 50 nm PtNPs (Figure S7B). For 50 nm, size was overestimated when these NPs were mixed with 1,500-2,000 ng L⁻¹ of ionic Pt (Figure S7A). For the mixture sample (30 and 50 nm PtNPs simultaneously), a misleading determination was obtained, since apparently, no overestimation was observed until 3,000 ng L⁻¹ of ionic Pt (Figure S7B). However, this is caused by an overestimation of the 30 nm PtNP distribution, which is incorrectly determined as 50 nm PtNPs.

Hence, it has been demonstrated that this method can be applied to follow size changes under situations where high ionic Pt is expected to be present, although under these conditions it can be limited for the accurate calculation of concentration.

3.4 Analytical characterization of the method

Working under the optimized data acquisition (Table 1) and deconvolution as data processing, a full analytical performance characterization of the method has been carried out for 30 nm PtNPs. The studied characteristics for PNC ($5.28 \cdot 10^4 \text{ p mL}^{-1}$) and size were trueness (referred as the closeness of agreement between the determined mean and the reference or expected values, %), intra-day precision (relative standard deviation in six replicates measured in the same day, $\text{RSD}_{\text{intra}}$), inter-day precision (relative standard deviation in samples measured in six different days, $\text{RSD}_{\text{inter}}$), and linearity (studied in a range between $1.06 \cdot 10^4$ to $3.02 \cdot 10^5 \text{ p mL}^{-1}$). All results are summarized in Table 3. Trueness close to 100 % for concentration and particle size were achieved when comparing the found and expected values, demonstrating the accuracy of the analysis. With respect to the precision, values below 2 % for concentration and below 1 % for size were found for intra- and inter-day precisions, respectively. In the same way, **good linearity** was reported in the studied range for concentration (**as represented in the scatterplot, Figure S8**). As presented early, low size (13.78 nm) and concentration (0.029 ng L^{-1}) **LODs** were reached. Nevertheless, to perform a complete analytical validation process, it would be required the existence of PtNP reference materials, which are not currently available.

Table 3. Analytical characteristics of the optimized SP-ICP-MS **method** in terms of mass concentration and size for trueness (expressed as mean and standard deviation ($n = 6$)), intra-day precision (RSD_{intra}), and inter-day precision (RSD_{inter}) for PtNPs (32 ± 3 nm at $5.28 \cdot 10^4$ p mL⁻¹).

	Mass concentration	Size
Trueness (%)	94 ± 8	100 ± 7
RSD_{intra} (%)	1.8	0.7
RSD_{inter} (%)	1.9	0.9

3.5 Determination of PtNPs in environmental and biological matrices

As stated early, PtNPs are present in almost all environmental compartments and organisms, and therefore, their monitoring would be interesting [26]. **Up to now**, SP-ICP-MS has been mainly used to study PtNPs in environmental samples, such as synthetic waters [22], road dust [27] or plants [23], although some application to biofluids has also been reported [20].

The applicability of the optimized **method** for the determination of PtNPs in complex biological samples has been evaluated **in the present work** using DMEM (directly, supplemented only with antibiotics, or with antibiotics and 10 % FBS). Also, **it has been tested** in moderately hard water (**Table S1**) without and with 2 mg L⁻¹ of HA, as an example of a proposed media for ecotoxicity tests involving nanomaterials [28], **and three real water samples** (tap water and two collected in the Tagus River, W #1-2, **characterization in Table S2**). The effect over concentration and size of different reagents previously used in the literature has been tested. Cysteine was selected based on other studies where it was employed to reduce the memory and matrix effects, improving the

LODs of other metals using ICP-MS based techniques [14]. In the same way, HCl has been typically used in environmental and biological analysis to reduce matrix effect and improve sensitivities [3]. Therefore, for this study, 30 nm PtNPs (at $5.28 \cdot 10^4 \text{ p Ml}^{-1}$) were mixed with 2 % HCl, 0.1 % Cys or a mixture of both, in each matrix.

For DMEM, there was no major size changes in the core size under any circumstances (Figure S9A). It can be related to the potential formation of a “bio-corona”, which typically occur to NPs in this kind of matrices, that may have conferred more stability to the PtNPs than their own coating, preventing the core from any clustering processes [29]. The formation of this interaction was reported for a variety of NPs in various biological matrices [30, 31]. As for PtNPs, it has been previously studied by Fernández-Trujillo *et al.* (2021) in the same cell culture media by means of HPLC-TQ-ICP-MS, where it was immediately observed. As a result of the formation of the bio-corona, a growth in the hydrodynamic diameters of PtNPs was reported, but aggregates, agglomerates, or relevant changes in their diameters were not observed using HR-SEM or DLS [32]. Regarding concentration determination (Figure S10A), no statistically significant differences were found ($p < 0.05$).

In contrast, interesting transformations have been observed in other matrices such as synthetic waters. Samples with Cysteine (0.1 % or mixture with HCl) experienced a growth on the mean determined diameter (Figure S9B). The formation of larger aggregates can be the responsible of this increase, as it can be checked regarding the particle size distributions (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Particle size distribution in presence of 2 % HCl (blue), 0.1 % Cys (red), a mixture of both (yellow) or none (black) for 30 nm PtNPs ($5 \cdot 10^4$ p ML^{-1}) in moderately hard water A) without or B) with ($2 \text{ mg } L^{-1}$) humic acid (HA).

In moderately hard water, those aggregates were only formed in samples with Cysteine (Figure 3A). This effect is also accompanied with a decrease in the concentration for 30 nm PtNP peak (Figure S10B). However, when organic matter ($2 \text{ mg } L^{-1}$ of HA) is added, those effects were diminished (Figure 3B), reducing the growth in the mean diameter and the concentration decrease. In this situation, a comparable effect to the one reported in

biological matrices seems to be happening. The interaction of the organic matter with the PtNPs results on the formation of a “eco-corona”, which also enhances their stability. This is a common transformation for NPs in the environment, being reported in various studies [33, 34]. Specifically for different sized PtNPs, the formation of this coating was also described in a previous work using AF4-ICP-MS, where the interaction of organic matter in synthetic waters was studied following changes in their hydrodynamic diameters [35]. Thus, when organic matter was present, aggregation was reduced, while their hydrodynamic diameters increased. Organic matter can either replace or overcoat PtNPs’ original coating, which ultimately increase their stability [35].

Finally, the proposed method was tested under real environmental conditions. PtNPs were spiked in tap water and two samples collected in the Tagus River (W #1 and #2). No differences on the average determined diameter were reported under any circumstances (Figure S9C) even though conductivity and hardness in the river waters are higher (Table S2) than in the synthetic water (Table S1). This can be explained through the formation of the “eco-corona” as previously observed in the synthetic water with organic matter. In all these samples, natural organic matter is present, which can result in the formation of the same entity, preventing any aggregation process. As for concentration (Figure S10C), no relevant differences were observed, following the same tendency than in previous samples.

4. Conclusions

The proposed method based on SP-ICP-MS using an underexploited deconvolution algorithm for data processing has been efficient to follow changes and transformations of PtNPs in relevant environmental and biological matrices, which would be interesting for toxicological and environmental fate studies. Although PtNPs have been used in this

study, the method shows great potential to be applied to other metallic NPs, since all the conditions are still general and not restricted or conditioned by Pt or the reference solution used for the transport efficiency calculations. In this sense, this approach can be used as a tool to assess other NPs in complex biological and environmental matrices.

The results of this work also highlight the need of a deep understanding of crucial SP-ICP-MS parameters and concepts, to reach harmonized methodologies or strategies to correctly perform any analysis using this approach. Also, there is an imperative necessity for the development and production of adequate reference materials for NP analysis, with certified size, and mass- and number-based concentration values. Thus, further research and inter-laboratory comparisons would be helpful in the advance to this technique maturity.

Declarations

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no competing interests.

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References

1. Bolea E, Jimenez MS, Perez-Arantegui J, et al (2021) Analytical applications of single particle inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry: a comprehensive and critical review. *Analytical Methods* 13:2742–2795. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1AY00761K>
2. Laborda F, Bolea E, Jiménez-Lamana J (2014) Single Particle Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry: A Powerful Tool for Nanoanalysis. *Anal Chem* 86:2270–2278. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac402980q>
3. Montañó MD, Olesik JW, Barber AG, et al (2016) Single Particle ICP-MS: Advances toward routine analysis of nanomaterials. *Anal Bioanal Chem* 408:5053–5074. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-016-9676-8>

4. Olesik JW, Gray PJ (2012) Considerations for measurement of individual nanoparticles or microparticles by ICP-MS: determination of the number of particles and the analyte mass in each particle. *J Anal At Spectrom* 27:1143. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2ja30073g>
5. Tuoriniemi J, Cornelis G, Hassellöv M (2012) Size Discrimination and Detection Capabilities of Single-Particle ICPMS for Environmental Analysis of Silver Nanoparticles. *Anal Chem* 84:3965–3972. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac203005r>
6. Resano M, Aramendía M, García-Ruiz E, et al (2022) Living in a transient world: ICP-MS reinvented *via* time-resolved analysis for monitoring single events. *Chem Sci* 13:4436–4473. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1SC05452J>
7. Pace HE, Rogers NJ, Jarolimek C, et al (2011) Determining Transport Efficiency for the Purpose of Counting and Sizing Nanoparticles via Single Particle Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry. *Anal Chem* 83:9361–9369. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac201952t>
8. Cuello-Nuñez S, Abad-Álvaro I, Bartczak D, et al (2020) The accurate determination of number concentration of inorganic nanoparticles using spICP-MS with the dynamic mass flow approach. *J Anal At Spectrom* 35:1832–1839. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9JA00415G>
9. Minelli C, Wywijas M, Bartczak D, et al (2022) Versailles project on advanced materials and standards (VAMAS) interlaboratory study on measuring the number concentration of colloidal gold nanoparticles. *Nanoscale* 14:4690–4704. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1NR07775A>
10. Peters R, Herrera-Rivera Z, Undas A, et al (2015) Single particle ICP-MS combined with a data evaluation tool as a routine technique for the analysis of nanoparticles in complex matrices. *J Anal At Spectrom* 30:1274–1285. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4JA00357H>
11. G. Cornelis (2022) Nanocount (version 3.2), Swedish Agricultural Sciences University.
12. Laborda F, Gimenez-Ingalature AC, Bolea E, Castillo JR (2020) About detectability and limits of detection in single particle inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry. *Spectrochim Acta Part B At Spectrosc* 169:105883. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sab.2020.105883>
13. Kaynarova LI, Georgieva DL, Stefanova VM (2022) An approach to estimate the contribution of signal noise to the diameter uncertainty of individual silver nanoparticles and resolution of spICP-MS analysis. *J Anal At Spectrom* 37:1484–1500. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ja00039c>
14. Cornelis G, Hassellöv M (2014) A signal deconvolution method to discriminate smaller nanoparticles in single particle ICP-MS. *J Anal At Spectrom* 29:134–144. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3JA50160D>
15. Bi X, Lee S, Ranville JF, et al (2014) Quantitative resolution of nanoparticle sizes using single particle inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry with the K-

- means clustering algorithm. *J Anal At Spectrom* 29:1630–1639. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ja00109e>
16. Jeyaraj M, Gurunathan S, Qasim M, et al (2019) A Comprehensive Review on the Synthesis, Characterization, and Biomedical Application of Platinum Nanoparticles. *Nanomaterials* 9:1719. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano9121719>
 17. Bundschuh M, Filser J, Lüderwald S, et al (2018) Nanoparticles in the environment: where do we come from, where do we go to? *Environ Sci Eur* 30:6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-018-0132-6>
 18. Laborda F, Jiménez-Lamana J, Bolea E, Castillo JR (2013) Critical considerations for the determination of nanoparticle number concentrations, size and number size distributions by single particle ICP-MS. *J Anal At Spectrom* 28:1220–1232. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3ja50100k>
 19. U.S. E.P.A. (2002) *Methods for Measuring the Acute Toxicity of Effluents and Receiving Waters to Freshwater and Marine Organisms Fifth Edition*
 20. Fernández-Trujillo S, Jiménez-Moreno M, Ríos Á, Martín-Doimeadios R del CR (2021) A simple analytical methodology for platinum nanoparticles control in complex clinical matrices via SP-ICP-MS. *Talanta* 231:122370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2021.122370>
 21. Sikder M, Wang J, Chandler GT, et al (2019) Synthesis, characterization, and environmental behaviors of monodispersed platinum nanoparticles. *J Colloid Interface Sci* 540:330–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2019.01.036>
 22. Sikder M, Wang J, Poulin BA, et al (2020) Nanoparticle size and natural organic matter composition determine aggregation behavior of polyvinylpyrrolidone coated platinum nanoparticles. *Environ Sci Nano* 7:3318–3332. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EN00659A>
 23. Jiménez-Lamana J, Wojcieszek J, Jakubiak M, et al (2016) Single particle ICP-MS characterization of platinum nanoparticles uptake and bioaccumulation by *Lepidium sativum* and *Sinapis alba* plants. *J Anal At Spectrom* 31:2321–2329. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6JA00201C>
 24. Geiss O, Bianchi I, Bucher G, et al (2022) Determination of the Transport Efficiency in spICP-MS Analysis Using Conventional Sample Introduction Systems: An Interlaboratory Comparison Study. *Nanomaterials* 12:725. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12040725>
 25. Lin F, Miyashita S, Inagaki K, et al (2019) Evaluation of three different sample introduction systems for single-particle inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (spICP-MS) applications. *J Anal At Spectrom* 34:401–406. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8JA00295A>
 26. Nejdil L, Kudr J, Blazkova I, et al (2015) *Platinum Metals in the Environment*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg

27. Folens K, van Acker T, Bolea-Fernandez E, et al (2018) Identification of platinum nanoparticles in road dust leachate by single particle inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry. *Science of The Total Environment* 615:849–856. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.09.285>
28. Geitner NK, Ogilvie Hendren C, Cornelis G, et al (2020) Harmonizing across environmental nanomaterial testing media for increased comparability of nanomaterial datasets. *Environ Sci Nano* 7:13–36
29. García-Álvarez R, Vallet-Regí M (2021) Hard and Soft Protein Corona of Nanomaterials: Analysis and Relevance. *Nanomaterials* 11:888. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11040888>
30. Soto-Alvaredo J, López-Chaves C, Sánchez-González C, et al (2017) Speciation of gold nanoparticles and low-molecular gold species in Wistar rat tissues by HPLC coupled to ICP-MS. *J Anal At Spectrom* 32:193–199. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6JA00248J>
31. López-Sanz S, Rodríguez Fariñas N, Rodríguez Martín-Doimeadios R. C, Ríos Á (2019) Analytical strategy based on asymmetric flow field flow fractionation hyphenated to ICP-MS and complementary techniques to study gold nanoparticles transformations in cell culture medium. *Anal Chim Acta* 1053:178–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2018.11.053>
32. Fernández-Trujillo S, Rodríguez Fariñas N, Jiménez-Moreno M, Rodríguez Martín-Doimeadios R.C. (2021) Speciation of platinum nanoparticles in different cell culture media by HPLC-ICP-TQ-MS and complementary techniques: A contribution to toxicological assays. *Anal Chim Acta* 1182:338935. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2021.338935>
33. Baalousha M, Afshinnia K, Guo L (2018) Natural organic matter composition determines the molecular nature of silver nanomaterial-NOM corona. *Environ Sci Nano* 5:868–881. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EN00018B>
34. Fischer J, Gräf T, Sakka Y, et al (2021) Ion compositions in artificial media control the impact of humic acid on colloidal behaviour, dissolution and speciation of CuO-NP. *Science of The Total Environment* 785:147241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147241>
35. Sánchez-Cachero A, López-Sanz S, Rodríguez Fariñas N, et al (2021) A method based on asymmetric flow field flow fractionation hyphenated to inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry for the monitoring of platinum nanoparticles in water samples. *Talanta* 222:121513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2020.121513>

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**Critical evaluation of key parameters in single particle
ICP-MS data processing for the correct determination
of platinum nanoparticles in complex environmental
and biological matrices**

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Supplementary text

1. Detailed reagents and chemicals.

HCl (37%) and HNO₃ (69%) were purchased from Scharlab (Spain), and Merck (Germany), respectively. All standards (Au, Pt and Tl, 1000 µg mL⁻¹) solutions were acquired from Inorganic Ventures (USA). NaCl, NaHCO₃, MgSO₄·7H₂O, and KCl were purchased from Panreac (Spain). CaSO₄·2H₂O was obtained from Probus (Spain). Humic acid (HA) sodium salt (H16752, molecular weight range 2-500 kDa), and L-Cysteine (> 98 %) were purchased from Merck (Germany).

Dulbecco's modified eagle medium (DMEM) high-glucose was purchased from Merck (Germany), while fetal bovine serum (FBS), penicillin and streptomycin were obtained from Lonza (Spain).

2. Characterization of NP solutions.

Nominal concentrations provided by the manufacturer were 54, and 55 µg mL⁻¹, for 30 and 50 nm PtNPs respectively, and 52 µg mL⁻¹ for 30 nm AuNPs. Also, nominal diameters provided by the manufacturer were 32 ± 3, and 51 ± 2, for 30 and 50 nm PtNPs, and 30 ± 3 nm for 30 nm AuNPs (measured by TEM). All solutions have been characterized in terms of concentration in our laboratory. Total platinum concentrations were 64 ± 2, and 48 ± 1 µg mL⁻¹ (n = 3) for 30 and 50 nm PtNPs respectively, and total gold concentration was 47 ± 4 for 30 nm gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), quantified by ICP-MS after microwave digestion as previously described elsewhere (Sánchez-Cachero *et al.*, 2021).

3. Optimization of other data acquisition parameters.

3.1. Dwell time

Dwell time is one of the most compelling data acquisition parameters in the determination of size and PNC (Olesik & Gray, 2012). A range of dwell times from 1 to 10 ms was investigated, using 30,000 data points and deconvolution as data processing algorithm for 30 nm PtNPs at a range of concentrations from $1.06 \cdot 10^4$ to $3.02 \cdot 10^5$ p mL⁻¹. Higher dwell times were not studied since the possibility of measuring double events raises. Lower ones were not considered due to a limitation in the software employed to do the data treatment in our work (Nanocount version 3.2), which needs the implementation of a peak detection step, that is not currently available. Obtained recoveries (%) are summarized in Figure S2.

Higher dwell times (7 and 10 ms) results in an overestimation of the recoveries at low PtNP concentrations (Figure S2), probably due to an increase of the baseline signal (and its standard deviation) and the combined uncertainty of the measurement for such long acquisition times (Kaynarova *et al.*, 2022). For 1 ms, a large number of incomplete events is measured, as it can be observed for the size determination (Figure S3), which also leads to low recoveries for low PtNP concentrations (Figure S2). No remarkable differences were observed between 3 and 5 ms in terms of either PNC determination or size (Figure S2 and S3). Even though both seem to be adequate for a correct study of PtNPs, 5 ms was selected as the optimum based on a previous work for this type of NPs where similar results were reported (Fernández-Trujillo *et al.*, 2021).

3.2. Data points

Another crucial parameter that has been investigated is the number of data points used to build the dataset of every sample. Statistically relevant dataset is required to improve concentration and size determination. A data point will be recorded every 5 ms (the optimized dwell time) during the selected acquisition time and, thus, the number of data points is directly controlled by it. It would be interesting to simplify the process finding the lowest data points value (and consequently time) needed to have accurate results. For this purpose, the same concentration range than in the previous section were also studied. The influence of data points from 5,000 to 40,000 (25 to 200 s of data acquisition) on the concentration and size determination was evaluated.

Recoveries (Figure S4) using smaller data points values (up to 20,000) were overestimated when sample concentrations were lower than $2.11 \cdot 10^4$ p mL⁻¹ due to the increase of false positives. No remarkable effect linked to the data point value was observed for the size determination since similar trends were reported for the different data points (Figure S5).

Larger data points values (30,000 and 40,000) enable a correct concentration determination for all the studied samples (Figure S4). Increasing the data points will minimize the possibilities to measure false positives and their total percentage in each sample's dataset. It will also reduce the scatter of the dataset and improve signal discrimination (Tuoriniemi *et al.*, 2012). 40,000 data points was selected as the optimum value. Moreover, it offers lower LOD_{size} and LOD_c (13.78 nm and 0.029 ng L⁻¹, respectively) than 30.000 data points (Deconvolution in Table 2), which will be helpful to apply the method for the analysis of environmental and biological samples, where low PtNP concentrations and unknown sizes are expected.

References to Supplementary

Fernández-Trujillo, S., Jiménez-Moreno, M., Ríos, Á., & Martín-Doimeadios, R. del C. R. (2021). A simple analytical methodology for platinum nanoparticles control in complex clinical matrices via SP-ICP-MS. *Talanta*, *231*, 122370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2021.122370>

Kaynarova, L. I., Georgieva, D. L., & Stefanova, V. M. (2022). An approach to estimate the contribution of signal noise to the diameter uncertainty of individual silver nanoparticles and resolution of spICP-MS analysis. *Journal of Analytical Atomic Spectrometry*, *37*(7), 1484–1500. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ja00039c>

Olesik, J. W., & Gray, P. J. (2012). Considerations for measurement of individual nanoparticles or microparticles by ICP-MS: determination of the number of particles and the analyte mass in each particle. *Journal of Analytical Atomic Spectrometry*, *27*(7), 1143. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2ja30073g>

Sánchez-Cachero, A., López-Sanz, S., Fariñas, N. R., Ríos, Á., & Martín-Doimeadios, R. del C. R. (2021). A method based on asymmetric flow field flow fractionation hyphenated to inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry for the monitoring of platinum nanoparticles in water samples. *Talanta*, *222*, 121513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2020.121513>

Tuoriniemi, J., Cornelis, G., & Hassellöv, M. (2012). Size Discrimination and Detection Capabilities of Single-Particle ICPMS for Environmental Analysis of Silver Nanoparticles. *Analytical Chemistry*, *84*(9), 3965–3972. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac203005r>

Supplementary figures

Figure S1. Mean diameter (nm) of A) 30 nm and B) 50 nm PtNPs using 5- σ criterion (blue), K-means (red), np-Quant (yellow), and deconvolution (black) as data processing method (5 ms as dwell time and, 30.000 data points for data acquisition).

Figure S2. Recoveries (%) for PtNP PNC ($p \text{ mL}^{-1}$) of 30 nm PtNPs using 1 (blue), 3 (red), 5 (yellow), 7 (black), and 10 (green) ms as dwell time, (30.000 data points for data acquisition and, deconvolution as data processing method).

Figure S3. Mean diameters (nm) for PtNP PNC ($p \text{ mL}^{-1}$) of 30 nm PtNPs using 1 (blue), 3 (red), 5 (yellow), 7 (black), and 10 (green) ms as dwell time, (30.000 data points for data acquisition and, deconvolution as data processing method).

Figure S4. Recoveries (%) for different PtNP PNC ($p \text{ mL}^{-1}$) using 5,000 (blue), 10,000 (red), 20,000 (black), 30,000 (yellow), and 40,000 (green) data points, (5 ms as dwell time and, deconvolution as data processing method).

Figure S5. Mean diameter (nm) of different PtNP PNC ($p \text{ mL}^{-1}$) using 5,000 (blue), 10,000 (red), 20,000 (black), 30,000 (yellow), and 40,000 (green) data points, (5 ms as dwell time and, deconvolution as data processing method).

A)

B)

C)

Figure S6. A) Raw data, B) Frequency histogram after deconvolution, and C) Size distribution of a mixture of 30 nm and 50 nm PtNPs solutions ($\approx 5 \cdot 10^4$ p mL⁻¹) analysed under optimized SP-ICP-MS operating conditions (Table 1).

Figure S7. Mean diameters (nm) of PtNPs solutions ($\approx 5 \cdot 10^4$ p mL⁻¹) at increasing ionic platinum concentrations for 30 nm (blue) and 50 nm (red) in individual samples (A), and a mixture of both PtNPs (30 nm in blue and 50 nm in red) (B).

Figure S8. Scatterplot representation of the regression line of the expected on the found *PtNP PNC*.

Figure S9. Mean diameter (nm) for 30 nm PtNPs ($5 \cdot 10^4$ p mL⁻¹) in A) DMEM (navy blue) and supplemented with antibiotics (blue), or with antibiotics and 10 % FBS (light blue), B) moderately hard water without (navy blue), and with (2 mg L^{-1}) humic acid (HA) (blue), and C) water samples W #1 (navy blue), W #2 (blue), and W #3 (light blue), in presence of various reagents (2 % HCl, 0.1 % Cys, or a mixture of both).

Figure S10. Recoveries (%) of 30 nm PtNPs ($5 \cdot 10^4 \text{ p mL}^{-1}$) in A) DMEM (navy blue), and supplemented with antibiotics (blue), or with antibiotics and 10 % FBS (light blue), B) moderately hard water without (navy blue), and with (2 mg L^{-1}) humic acid (HA) (blue), and C) different water samples, W #1 (navy blue), W #2 (blue), W #3 (light blue), in presence of various reagents (2 % HCl, 0.1 % Cys, or a mixture of both).

Supplementary tables

Table S1. Composition and characterization of synthetic moderately hard water sample

Sample	Concentration (mM)				Ionic Strength (mM)	pH*	Conductivity* ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	Hardness** 12.412(mg L ⁻¹ CaCO ₃)
	NaHCO ₃	CaSO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	KCl				
Moderately Hard	1.14	0.35	0.5	0.05	4.6	7.8 ± 0.2	312 ± 7	80 – 100

*Mean and standard deviation ($n = 3$)

**Values provided by the U.S. E.P.A.

Table S2. Characteristics of different water samples. Mean and standard deviation ($n = 3$)

Sample	GPS coordinates	pH	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	Hardness (mg L ⁻¹ CaCO ₃)	Organic matter (mg L ⁻¹ O ₂)	Ca ²⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	Mg ²⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	Cl ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)
Tap water	39.865680, -4.041239	6.88 ± 0.17	170 ± 3	37	1.29 ± 0.12	12.40 ± 0.57	1.46 ± 0.34	16.8 ± 1.1
W #1	40.237883, -2.976429	8.04 ± 0.12	781 ± 7	430	1.59 ± 0.14	132.0 ± 1.0	24.5 ± 1.3	36.20 ± 0.90
W #2	40.236429, -2.982026	8.24 ± 0.16	765 ± 5	428	1.640 ± 0.070	131.0 ± 1.0	24.6 ± 1.4	38.40 ± 0.90

Table S3. Recoveries (%) and size (nm) obtained (expressed as mean and standard deviation) using different methods for transport efficiency calculation. Expected value for size was 32 ± 3 nm

Method	Transport efficiency (%) (n=3)	Recoveries (%) (n=6)	Size (nm) (n=6)
Direct (PtNPs)	10 ± 1	94 ± 8	32 ± 3
Direct (AuNPs)	7.5 ± 0.4	87 ± 4	32 ± 2
Gravimetric*	8.8 ± 0.2	88 ± 4	31 ± 2

*Ref. 8